

The Reality of Using Social Networks in Technical Colleges in Palestine

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify the reality of the use of social networks in the technical colleges in Palestine, where the variables of social networks were included. The analytical descriptive method was used in the study. A questionnaire consisting of (12) items was randomly distributed to college workers Technology in the Gaza Strip. The sample of the study consisted of (205) employees of these colleges. The response rate was 74.5%.

The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the social networks and a relative weight (74.15%) according to the perspective of the employees of the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The results of the study showed that there is a high level of social networking areas (site management and Website Content) in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The field of site management ranked first with a relative weight of 74.91%, and second and last (Content Site) with a relative weight (73.38%). The results showed that there were differences between colleges in the use of social networks where the results showed that the most common colleges used these networks (UCAS) and the least used is (GTC). The results showed no differences between male and female employees in the use of social networks in technical colleges.

The researchers suggest a number of recommendations, including: the need to raise awareness of the importance of Facebook and other social networking sites, through the holding of courses for employees in technical colleges, and to identify the ways to optimize the use of such sites, and the benefits of this use, and reflected positively on technical colleges. And the adoption of dealing with the various social networking sites as a reality, and the Palestinian and Arab technical colleges, use them in accordance with the objectives of technical colleges. Advise the Department of Technical Colleges to devote time to their presence on social networks to follow the public and respond to their queries. There is a need for the attention of decision-makers in technical colleges in social sites, because they are considered an important and effective means of communication, and the link between beneficiaries and decision-makers. There is a need to promote the use of modern electronic means of work and the need to increase the link of customers to the college through electronic services.

Keywords: social networking, site management, Website Content, technical colleges.

1. INTRODUCTION

The great technological development has led to a qualitative shift in all aspects of life (economic, social, political, cultural, etc.). The most prominent of these developments is the emergence of the Internet, which has spread widely throughout the world, which made it look like a small village.

The social networks that have proliferated and the number and the number of its users on the web represent a new revolution in communication, since it has allowed, for the first time in human history, the instantaneous and interactive communication between people connected to the Internet through classified groups of common interests and without intermediaries, as was the case in traditional feedstock, or even on websites and e-newspapers that are also traditional by the standards of these new networks.

The Internet is one of the fastest-growing methods of modern communication. Internet communication has gone through several phases until the emergence of so-called social networking sites, one of the important uses of the Internet. These sites enable the user to participate and contribute to the creation (Al-Mekdadi, 2013).

The impact of the use of social networks was not limited to the exchange of information between individuals but rather to electronic marketing activities, where many companies published their information and offered their products and services through social networks (Al-Sumaidi, 2012). The number of Internet users reached 3 billion worldwide, representing 50% of the world's population, which in turn reflected the number of users of social networks (Laudon, 2014).

With the increasing global and Arab attention to the phenomenon of social networks and their impact on the individual and society, and with the multiplicity of research approaches that study this phenomenon in all dimensions, this study comes to reveal the reality of the use of social networks in technical colleges in Palestine.

2. THE GENERAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

2.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem of the study is focused on the study of researchers through the follow-up to the Web, the decline of social networking sites, and the impact of these networks on the audience of recipients, where contemporary life is changing in many ways as the world keeps pace with technical progress accompanied by a population explosion and

knowledge, there is a consensus among many of researchers that modern communication technology, especially the Internet has opened a new era of communication and interaction between people and the abundance of information and knowledge provided to users, and benefited each browser to this network of multimedia available in it and became the best way to achieve communication between individuals and groups, and then appeared Web pages on the Internet, some of them to advertise the goods and services or to sell products, and the opportunity for discussion between browsers, until the emergence of social networks, such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube and others, where social networking sites are the most popular on the Internet, because of the characteristics that distinguished it from the websites, which encouraged Internet surfers from around the world to the increasing demand Where the information network linked people to each other The social networking sites have invaded all areas of social life as a means of communication and exchange of ideas and information as well as political and economic and education fields.

All companies and institutions always strive to measure their ability to meet the needs of the public and to meet their needs, which requires them to use the latest innovative ways and means to reach this goal. Recently, there has been a new way in this field which has proven to be successful in reaching customers and to know their views continuously and simultaneously, social networks that have become the largest gathering in the world. The study of (Halasa, 2013) indicated the importance of the adoption by organizations of social networks in their strategic planning, in order to contribute to the achievement of their various objectives, while focusing on the care and benefit of the public.

There have been many studies that dealt with the phenomenon of the use of social networks after they entered these networks to homes and cafes and increased the number of users, Al-Masri (2011) found that 52% of respondents use social networking sites for up to two hours per day.

Based on the above, and through the researchers' knowledge of previous studies related to the subject of the research, the researchers studied the reality of the use of social networks in the technical colleges in Palestine. The problem of the study can be expressed in the following question:

Q1- What is the reality of the use of social networks in technical colleges in Palestine?

2.2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study tries through its axes to achieve the following objectives:

1. Examining the reality of the use of social networks in technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.
2. To reveal the viewpoint of technical colleges' employees about the services provided by the social networking sites and to what extent they are related to their concerns.
3. Identify the reasons that have helped to diversify the attitudes of technical college staff towards social networking sites.
4. Put forward the most important issues that contribute to the use of technology to develop the performance of technical education.
5. To arrive at a test of the validity of the hypotheses of the study.
6. To come up with conclusions and recommendations for the technical colleges in question.

2.3 RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

1. The scientific significance of the research is that this subject highlights a new topic that is developing rapidly because of the relevance of the subject to the technology that develops day by day. The subject of the study can be counted from the new subjects. And researchers, to go more into the social networking.
2. The researchers expect this study to be an important reference for researchers and scholars. This study will contribute to enriching the libraries and the Arab and international academic arena with new research studies and studies. The study will benefit specifically scientific research institutions in academic studies, especially in the field of social networks
3. The importance of the applied study is that it has shed light on the extent to which the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip keep abreast of the modern systems, concepts and administrative models, and the role it plays in achieving the goals of the technical colleges through the use of social media, in addition to the different methods used by the technical colleges.
4. The researchers hope that the results of this study will contribute to increasing the interest of technical colleges in the use of social networks.
5. The importance of the study is how to provide the services provided by technical colleges on the Internet and on the website of technical colleges on the network so that the largest possible use of them around the clock, which

helps the technical colleges to communicate with the largest number of students and beneficiaries and deal with them.

2.4 RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

In order to provide an appropriate answer to the questions posed, and the study seeks to test the validity of the following assumptions:

H01: There is a high level of use of social networks in technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.

H02: There are statistically significant differences at the level of a ≤ 0.05 in the dimensions of the use of social networks depending on the college variable.

H03: There are statistically significant differences at the level of a ≤ 0.05 in the dimensions of the use of social networks depending on the gender variable

2.5 RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

1. **Subject Limit (Academic):** The study was limited in its objective to study the reality of the use of social networks in technical colleges in Palestine.
2. **Human Limit:** The study was conducted on the responses of workers in the technical colleges under study.
3. **Institutional Limit:** The study was conducted on the major technical colleges in the Gaza governorates in the State of Palestine.
4. **The spatial dimension:** The study was conducted in the State of Palestine and was limited to the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip (Palestine Technical College - Dair Al-Balah, Gaza Training Community College (GTC), Al-Azhar University College of Applied Sciences, Al-Aqsa Society College).
5. **Time Limits:** The study was conducted and preliminary data collected on the technical colleges and statistical analyzes were carried out during the period (2018). Therefore, it represents the reality at this time.

3. RESEARCH TERMINOLOGY

- **Technician:** A person who occupies a middle position between the engineer and the technologist on the one hand and the skilled worker on the other. He has the task of applying the technical practices. He has the scientific knowledge, professional skills and technical expertise that helps him to diagnose the problems and develop the details. He is responsible for transforming the engineer designs into an integrated production process (Al-Shahry, 1995). The task of the technical team is the middle jobs in the production sites and intermediate administrative works and they form the mainstay of the production and service process because they are professionally considered as the operational working link between the various categories of specialists of engineers, trade and others and among the categories of technical workers who work in all the institutions on which the economy is based (Al-Saeed, 2006).
- **Technical colleges:** are regular educational institutions with duration of between 2-3 years after high school and without first-degree students (Mustafa, 2001). Technical colleges have recently been interested in analytical abilities and innovative skills as well as more Modern technologies, adaptation, operation and maintenance, and the training of technicians to absorb the rapid and complex transformations in order to meet the needs of the production and service sectors. Hence, many countries have started to award university degrees and masters and doctorate degrees such faculty's High technology in the United Arab Emirates, which grants bachelor's degree in Engineering Technology (Al-Issa, 2004).
- **Technical Education:** This is the type of formal higher education that includes educational preparation and imparting the skills and technical knowledge that are carried out by regular educational institutions not less than two years after secondary school to prepare a workforce in different disciplines (Al-Abd, 2001).
The researchers defines technical education as: education that earns individuals the knowledge, skills and trends that qualify them to join the labor market in a technical work and study two years after high school.
- **Social networks:** Social web sites are the mainstay of new or alternative media, which allows individuals and groups to communicate among themselves through this virtual space (Sadiq, 2008). It is also known as: interactive social networks that allow users to communicate at any time they wish and anywhere in the world. They have been on the internet for years and also enable them to communicate visually and share the images and other potentials that strengthen their social relationship (Al-Dulaimi, 2011). It is a collection of tools that have emerged because of the Internet, which has attracted a wide range of users of all ages, providing them with the opportunity to communicate and interact with them through photos, video clips and audio, as well as linking with other websites. It also allowed many other features that gave the user more freedom, which led to user retention (Berkbek, 2015). Another definition of social networking was defined as "the use of the Internet to communicate and communicate with the poor" (Al-Mekdadi, 2013).

- **Procedural definition of social networks:** It is an online social networking site that allows colleges and beneficiaries through the management of the site and its content to communicate with each other through the virtual world at anytime and anywhere, so that they can communicate visually and audio, share photos and other potentials that strengthen the social relationship. Among them, in addition to reaching as much mutual benefit as possible among them.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed to identify the reality of technical education in Palestine. The analytical descriptive method was used in the study. A questionnaire which consisted of 41 paragraphs was distributed randomly to the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. Random sample of (275) employees of these colleges were used, and the response rate was (74.5%). The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of technical education with a relative weight of 76.07%. The ranking and relative weight was as follows: Technical education institutions: 79.51%, graduates of technical education 75.75%, Labor market and local community 72.96%. The researchers propose a number of recommendations, the most important of which is: the need to pay attention to technical education in line with the National Strategic Plan for Higher Education by moving towards technical education. The importance of offering special courses in all technical education programs in these colleges. The researchers urged more future studies that address the same variables as the current study and apply them to other sectors.
- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed to identify the creative environment and its relation to the graceful management of the technical colleges operating in Gaza Strip. The analytical descriptive method was used through a questionnaire which was randomly distributed to 289 employees of the technical colleges in Gaza Strip with a total number of (1168) employees and a response rate equal to (79.2%) of the sample study. The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the creative environment with a relative weight of (75.19%). It also showed a high level of creative environment where the ranking and relative weight was as follows: Fluency (76.86%), Sensation of problems (74.89%), Flexibility (74.59%) and originality (74.41%). The results showed that the technical colleges achieved a high level of agile management with a relative weight of 76.69% and a high level of agile management. (79.56%), responding to customer requirements (79.14%), reducing costs (75.68%), maximizing competitiveness and profitability (74.59%), Improve service (74.52%), and the results showed a statistically significant difference relationship between the dimensions of the creative environment and management in agile technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The researchers suggested a number of recommendations, the most important of which is the need to enhance the dimensions of the creative environment by working to improve the abilities of the faculties in fluency, flexibility, originality, sensitivity to problems and the importance of increasing attention to the dimensions of achieving the graceful management because of their role in the development of technical education departments and sustainability. Develop agile management mechanisms and applications in terms of reducing waste, reducing costs, improving service, responding to customer requirements, and maximizing competitiveness and profitability, commensurate with the capabilities of these colleges.
- Study of (Abu Naser et al., 2017) aimed to identify the technical education and its role in promoting entrepreneurship in Gaza Strip. The analytical descriptive method was used in the study. A questionnaire was composed of (41) items and distributed randomly by the technical colleges in Gaza Strip using stratified random sample of (275) employees from the mentioned colleges, and the response rate was (74.5%). The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of technical education with a relative weight of 76.07%. The ranking and relative weights were as follows: Technical education institutions: 79.51%, graduates of technical education 75.75% Labor market and local community 72.96%. The results of the study showed that the technical colleges achieved a high level of promotion of entrepreneurship with a relative weight of 73.45%. Where the ranking and relative weights were as follows: competitive assault (76.65%), creative orientation (74.96%), preparedness (74.07%) and risk (68.39%). The results also confirmed a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of technical education and the promotion of entrepreneurship in technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The results also confirmed a statistically significant impact of technical education on the promotion of entrepreneurship in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The researchers proposed a number of recommendations, the most important: the need to go to technical education because of its role in the promotion of entrepreneurship, the importance of linking technical education and promoting entrepreneurship to the Palestinian society in general and the Gaza Strip in particular, the need to pay attention to technical education in line with the National Strategic Plan for Higher Education by moving towards technical education, and the importance of urging decision-makers in technical colleges to promote interest in leadership and to put their

own courses in all technical education programs in these colleges. The researchers urged further studies of the same variables as the current study of entrepreneurship and their application to other sectors.

- Study of (Abu Naser et al., 2017) aimed to identify the social networks and their role in achieving the effectiveness of electronic marketing for technical colleges in the Gaza Strip, which included variables of social networks and their role in electronic marketing, as well as the recognition of the existence of differences of statistical significance in the attitudes of respondents towards the variables of the study, and using a descriptive analytical approach in the study. A questionnaire of 50 items was randomly distributed among the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The sample of the study was composed of (275) employees of these colleges. The response rate was 74.5%. The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of social networks and a relative weight (74.15%). There is a high level of social networking areas (site management (74.91%), content of the site: (73.38%)). The technical colleges achieved a high level of use of electronic marketing, where the total relative weight (70.24%). There is a high level of e-marketing (Electronic advertising (71.75%), electronic promotion (74.75%), news groups (66.03%), and communication with the audience (student) (68.73%)). There is a statistically significant relationship between the organization's smart dimensions and sustainability in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The results also confirmed that there is a statistically significant impact of social networks in e-marketing in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip. The researchers proposed a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: Adopting dealing with the various social media sites as a reality on the Palestinian and Arab technical colleges, using them in accordance with the objectives of the technical colleges. The need to direct marketing through social networks and the exploitation of this network in marketing through them, the follow-up of the pages of the colleges and open the door of dialogue, communication, and respond to all inquiries. Technical colleges should put electronic marketing in their strategic marketing plan.
- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed at identify technical colleges as smart organizations and their relation to sustainability. The variables of smart organizations included: "Strategic vision, culture of merit and excellence, incentive system" and its relation to sustainability, which included three main dimensions (innovation, processes, and environmental aspects of the community). The questionnaire was composed of (39) items, which were randomly distributed to the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The sample of the study consisted of 289 employees from the mentioned colleges. The response rate was (79.2%). The results showed a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the smart organization and relative weight (71.42%) according to the perspective of the employees of the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. Where the field (culture of merit and skill) ranked first and with relative weight (73.76%), followed by strategic vision and relative weight (72.62%), and finally came the area (incentive program) in the third and last place and a relative weight (67.91%). The results of the study showed that the technical colleges achieved a level high in sustainability in its operations with total relative weight (73.33%). Where the field (environmental aspects of society) came first and with relative weight (73.97%), followed by innovation and relative weight (73.10%), and finally came the field (operations) ranked third and last and relative weight (72.92%). The results confirmed a statistically significant relationship between the organization's smart dimensions and sustainability in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The researchers propose a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: to enhance the dimensions of the smart organization in the technical colleges by improving the incentive program, developing the strategic vision and then supporting the culture of merit and skill. And increasing attention to the dimensions of achieving sustainability because of their role in the development and sustainability of technical education through the promotion and improvement of operations in technical colleges. He urged senior management and decision-makers to work in technical colleges to create, innovate and reward and support their creators.
- Study of (Al-Hayek, 2017) which aims at understanding the relationship between the use of marketing through social networks and enhancing the relationship with the customer within the information technology companies in the Gaza Strip. The research concluded with many results, the most important of which is that there is a statistically significant relationship between marketing through social networks, and customer relationship management in IT companies in the Gaza Strip. There are no statistically significant differences on marketing through social networks, and customer relationship management is due to the variable (gender, age, years of experience, qualification, specialization). There are statistically significant differences about marketing through social networks, and customer relationship management is due to the variable (job title, sector in which the company operates).
- Study of (Ajour, 2016) Which aimed at understanding the impact of the use of social networks as a tool to create a brand of the operator, to know the impact of this on the perception of the job seekers to attract the brand of the operator, and the main results of this study that there is a relationship between the different media used by

the operator, and the perception of job seekers The operator's brand attractiveness, as well as the impact that enterprises use for social networking to build their brand, This is reflected in the recognition of job seekers by the attractiveness of this brand. The most important recommendations of this study were that companies should pay attention to their different pages through social networks and focus on more than one network. Companies should use different methods and methods of social communication. A trained human being has the ability to respond to public comments and queries.

- Study of (Berkbek, 2015) The aim of this study was to determine the extent to which the political elite relied on the social networks as the main source of information during the Israeli aggression on the Gaza Strip in 2014 and the extent of their follow-up and the reasons for their follow-up. The main results of this study were that 78% of the respondents relied on social networking sites to obtain information, and that 76% of them were following the social networking sites in order to obtain information, and Facebook came in the forefront of social networks that are Relied on during the aggression to obtain information and then tension and then YouTube.
- Study of (Aniemeka, Emmanuel, 2013) which aimed at identifying the opportunities provided by social networks in supporting education in Africa and the impact of social networks on the economy, the researcher studied four Nigerian universities. The researcher relied on interviews and focus groups with the students of these universities as tools for collecting information. Study that social networks can be used as a new educational tool that will delight universities and students and can open the field of education in ways and methods. In addition, social networking networks are easy to access, whether from a computer or laptop, the ability to track what is new is easy, time-consuming, or easy to read. Effort. One of the main recommendations of this study was the possibility of working on all disciplines and thus adopting social networks as a reliable learning tool.
- Study of (Halasa, 2013) which aimed to identify the reality of the use of social networks in the Gaza Strip by social institutions in enhancing their relationship with the public. The study found that there is a negative relationship between the use of social networks by social institutions to enhance their relationship with the public, and that these institutions use social networks to achieve public satisfaction and reduce public complaints. The study found that the community institutions working in the Gaza Strip must adopt in a serious manner and according to a planned plan the use of social networks to contribute to the achievement of their goals.
- Cox (2012), which aimed to clarify how to use the social networks of small start-ups and how these networks, can be used for small businesses, targeted Facebook and Twitter. The main results of this study were strategies to demonstrate how to use the Facebook and Twitter In favor of small businesses and to focus on customers and sales, and focus on the content that is published by this company through its own accounts on the basis of S social networking.

Comment on previous studies

There is no doubt that previous studies are of great importance to all academic researchers, institutes, universities, research centers, or research companies and institutions when conducting any scientific research that is reliable and may benefit from these studies researchers or other research bodies, whether they relate to their research topics or approaching them. To answer the questions of the study and formulate its hypotheses and achieve its objectives, through which the researchers arrive at the results and conclusions and proposals may contribute to enrich their research topics, which would compensate for the shortage of studies that preceded it, and notes that most of the previous studies adopted by the researchers in this study, although limited, has to some extent addressed some of the main aspects of this study. After reviewing previous studies, the researchers show the extent of interest in social networks and the use of social networks as a marketing tool. And what are the similarities and differences, in addition to showing what distinguishes this search for others.

1. References from previous studies:

Through the study of the researchers of previous studies have achieved many benefits, which helped researchers in the completion of this study, and these benefits:

- Help researchers identify the problem and questions of the study.
- Identification of study variables.
- Formulation of hypotheses.
- Identify the study community.
- Selection of the methodology of the study, its tools and statistical methods?
- Building the theoretical framework.

– Formulation and identification of questionnaire questions

2. What distinguishes this study from previous studies:

- Previous studies have mostly addressed the importance of social networks in many aspects, including social and educational, and did not take into account the perspective of workers in the institutions themselves.
- In terms of studies on social networks, most of the previous studies concerned social networks in general, and social networks were used as a tool to promote research and were not focused on.
- This study is the first of its kind to the knowledge of researchers, which examines the reality of the use of social networks in the technical colleges in Palestine and presents the ways and methods provided by social networks.

5. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Social networks

The Internet is a collection of websites that contain a huge amount of information in various fields and on all levels. The website is usually one page or several pages, and contains a set of topics, video files, pictures and others, and any user can access the Internet Access to these available sites at any time, and access in a few seconds to any information they want from their main sources and anywhere in the world.

Social networking is one of the outcomes of Web 2.0 technology, without which we would not have been able to access this digital advance in all areas of life. This technology is based on social networks, which derive their strength from the interaction of users themselves.

The main idea of the social networks is to collect the data of the members who are subscribed to the site and publicize this data so that members of common interests meet and search for files or images. etc, that is, a network of effective sites that facilitate social life between a set of knowledge Friends, and old friends can communicate with each other and after years of being able to communicate visually, voice, share pictures and other potentials that strengthen social relationships (Jarar, 2011). Social networking sites are also defined as a system of electronic networks over the Internet that allows the subscriber to create a special site and then connect it through an electronic social system with other members who have the same interests and hobbies (Radi, 2003).

These social sites allow users to share files, share pictures and share videos, and enable them to create blogs, instant chat, and send messages. Social networks have three main sites: Facebook, Twitter, and the location of videos YouTube. It has become the primary means of exchanging information and instant news in monitoring the course and developments of events (Al- Mansour, 2012). The following figure (1) illustrates the most important social networks in the world and the number of users until the date (1/2017), highlighting the importance of these networks in linking the world with each other.

Figure 1: The most important social networks

Sources: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users>, (2018)

Here are six of the most important social networking networks: Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, Google+, LinkedIn.

Since the first appearance of the social networking sites, there have been many and varied between personal and public networks aspiring to achieve specific goals, "commercial, for example". Since its inception, the sites that lead the list have varied from one year to the next. Historically, the site of Six Diffusion has been of great importance and wide resonance with its early beginnings, the classification of which comes in view of the As well as the site "Omay News" and others. With the development of social networking sites has become classified comes in view of mass topping the list where a number of networks, most notably: Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, which we are talking about as the most important social networking sites at the moment and so given the different specialization of each site.

First- Facebook

Facebook is the world's most popular social networking tool. It started as a public school project (2005) by Mark Zuckerberg at the age of 19 years and then started in 2006. Although Harvard University refused to fund the idea with funds to launch his project, he challenged it and decided to do it with his friends (Kirkpatrick, 2010). In the present era, there is no Internet user who does not have a Facebook account, which is available in all the languages of the world, and is no longer just a means of dating but has become an advertising, marketing and promotional platform that comes second only to Google. Facebook's enormous potential as a tool for social change stems from its ability to reach and link up to 1.6 billion people, making it a marketing tool for social companies and building virtual communities that share a particular area or interest (Duffy, 2016).

Second- YouTube

It is a US platform established in 2005 to share multimedia among its subscribers. It was acquired by Google in 2006 against \$1.65 billion. The site allows users to download multimedia, view, rate, share, add to favorites, and comment on videos. Watching videos on the Internet is more popular than ever, due to the proliferation of broadband Internet packages, increased social networking, continuous updating of sites such as Facebook and Twitter, and the ability to embed YouTube links within a huge number of websites.

Third- Twitter

Founded in 2006 as a news network in the United States of America, it became a social network after its success due to the use of a 140-page SMS system. Currently, this service employs 317 million people worldwide. In the world. Although some do not regard it as a social network like Facebook, it is widely recognized by many organizations as having great value in getting their own marketing and advertising information by following the responses of the two lovers (Lovejoy and Saxton, 2012). Twitter has created powerful, niche communities on its social network, but these communities are not well used by social organizations. Instead, tweets are sent to collect donations or tweets containing information and informational messages.

Fourthly- Instagram

The use of Instagram has spread widely among Internet users during the first two months of its launch to 1 million users. Within one year of its launch, the number of users has doubled to reach 5 million users by late 2011. Since the start of downloading on the Android system support devices, to the number of users thirty million users, and in just one year the total number. Through online social networking, Instagram has begun worldwide in the last quarter of 2010 for iPhone and iPad users. In 2012, Instagram developed the site to include Android phones, It can be downloaded (Instagram) by searching for it in Google Play and iTunes.

Fifthly- Google+

Google+ is one of the services provided by the famous giant Google. This service is one of the many social networking services such as Twitter and Facebook. Google+ has the positive and technical features it has, and distinguishes it from other social networks, while at the same time having its own disadvantages. One of the positive features of Google+ is that it has a maximum privacy for the users of the service; it has privacy that does not have other social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, etc. It also has many techniques, methods and methods, Social networks, such as the diversity of video and video display, user-to-user conversations, and the features of identifying and sharing knowledge, friends, and relatives into circles and circles. Each circle or episode can be granted limited access by the owner of the accounts on Google+.

Sixthly- LinkedIn

LinkedIn is one of the most popular networks where companies search for qualified and experienced employees in a particular area of work based on what a person delivers in his / her profile via the network (Foura, 2012). It is a professional social network, It is similar to the Facebook network, but it is intended for work and its objectives, not for communication. The most important thing that is used by this network is easy access to employees or work. It is

easy to search and find the right people to work by They have this network (Berbek, 2015). LinkedIn is business-oriented, marketing services, and possible to publish paid ads, and the network provides user reports.

6. FIELD STUDY

First- Research Methodology

This study is based on the analytical descriptive approach to describe and describe the phenomenon to be studied as it exists. In fact, researchers in this approach are considering the study of tools, phenomena and practices existing and available for study and measurement as they are, without the intervention of the researchers in their course, and researchers can interact with them and describe them and analyze them scientifically and objectively.

The study relies on two basic types of data:

1. **Initial Data:** The study was carried out in the field by distributing questionnaires to study the vocabulary of the study, collecting and gathering the necessary information in the subject of the study, and then unloading and analyzing it using the statistical program (SPSS) and using the appropriate statistical tests in order to arrive at indications of value and indicators that support the subject of the study. And some personal interviews conducted by the researchers with those involved in order to obtain some undocumented data in writing and to clarify some views.
2. **Secondary data:** through the review of books, periodicals, special publications, scientific and professional journals related to the subject of the study, and any references contribute to enrich the study in a scientific way, and the researchers through the use of secondary sources in the study to identify the foundations and scientific methods sound in writing studies, A general overview of the latest developments that took place in the field of study.

Second- Study Population:

The study population consists of all employees in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip (Palestine Technical College - Deir Al-Balah, Gaza Training Community College, College of Intermediate Studies- Al-Azhar, University College of Applied Sciences, Al-Aqsa Society College). The study population may be (964) of the employees of the technical colleges under study as follows:

Table 1: illustrates the study population

The College	Number Of Employees	The Ratio%
Palestine Technical College - Deir Al-Balah	193	%20
Gaza Training Community College	119	%12.34
College of Intermediate Studies- Al-Azhar	184	%19.09
University College of Applied Sciences	335	%34.75
Al-Aqsa Society College	133	%13.79
Total	964	%100

Source: Prepared by researchers by reference to the statistical book and the annual statistical guide for Palestinian higher education institutions, Ministry of Education and Higher Education.(2016)

Third- The study sample:

1. A survey sample was used by the researchers to verify the validity and reliability of these tools. The sample size was 32 employees.
2. The sample is random and consists of (275) employees of these colleges. The response rate was 74.5%.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents from the sample of the study

Personal Data	Category	The Number	The Ratio%
Gender	Male	157	%85.3
	Female	48	%23.4
	Total	205	100%
The college	Palestine Technical College	30	14.63%
	Gaza Training Community College	31	15.12%
	College of Intermediate Studies- Al-Azhar	47	22.92%
	College of Applied Sciences	45	21.95%
	Al-Aqsa Society College	52	25.36%
	Total	205	100%

Table 2 shows that:

(85.3%) of the study sample were male, and (23.4%) were females, (17.07%) of the sample had an average age of less than 30 years, (56.58%) aged from 30 and less than 40 year where the highest category, (17.07%) aged from 40 to less than 50 years, and (9.26%) of those aged 50 and above. This indicates that the technical colleges in Gaza Strip are new colleges and that they attract the youth group to work and that they support the young people.

As for the college variable, Al-Aqsa Society College came in first place with a percentage of (25.36%) as it is a government college. Among the general orientations of the Ministry of Education is the orientation towards technical education. Therefore, there is a keenness from the Ministry to provide government colleges with the needs they need. The Faculty of Intermediate Studies - Al Azhar ranked second by (22.92%), the University College of Applied Sciences came third (21.95%), followed by the Gaza Community Training Society, followed by the fourth (15.12%), and then came in the last rank of the Technical College of Palestine, which received a percentage of (14.63%).

Fourthly- Study tool:

Since the nature of the hypotheses and the variables included in them are the ones that control the choice of the appropriate tool, accordingly, the researchers have prepared a measure for that study commensurate with its objectives and hypotheses. The process of designing and preparing the study scale has gone through several stages and steps:

1. See previous studies on the subject of the present study.
2. Collect and define scale paragraphs.
3. Formulation of the standard expressions according to the study sample.
4. Set the meter instructions.
5. How to correct the meter.
6. Conduct a study of stability and honesty of the scale.

How to correct the meter:

The five-dimensional Likert scale was used to measure respondents' responses to the questionnaire sections according to the following table:

Table 3: The degrees of the five-dimensional Likert scale

Response	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Class	1	2	3	4	5

Validate the measure: The researchers calculated the validity of the meter in the following ways:

1. **Virtual honesty:** The researchers verified the authenticity of the tool ostensibly by presenting it to a group of PhD holders in Business Administration (8). The apparent honesty indicates the general appearance of the test in terms of its relevance to the subjects, the relevance of the phrase to the field, and the clarity of the wording and instructions.
2. **Internal consistency:** The researchers calculated the validity of the internal consistency of the scale by finding the correlation coefficients between each field and the total score of the scale. The researchers conducted honesty and persistence on a sample of 32 employees by finding correlation coefficients for each paragraph in the field to which they belong. The following tables:

Table 4: Validity coefficients for each paragraph with the total score of its field in the scale of the social networks

Website Administration			Website Content		
Paragraph Number	Honesty Coefficient	Level Of Significance	Paragraph Number	Honesty Coefficient	Level Of Significance
1	0.427	0.05	1	0.768	0.01
2	0.518	0.01	2	0.711	0.01
3	0.517	0.01	3	0.804	0.01
4	0.524	0.01	4	0.832	0.01
5	0.417	0.05	5	0.778	0.01

6	0.468	0.01	6	0.772	0.01
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Stability of the scale:

The concept of stability means the ability of the test to give the same grades or values to the same individual or individuals if the measurement process is repeated. To ensure the stability of the scale, the researchers used the following methods:

1. **The method of split-half:** By calculating the correlation coefficient between the odd and even numbered questions, and obtained the stability coefficients as shown in the following table:

Table 5: Stability coefficient of social networks

No.	Field	Number Of Item	Correlation Coefficient Before Adjustment	Correlation Coefficient After Adjustment	Level Of Significance
1.	Website Administration	6	0.709	0.803	Sig. at 0.01
2.	Website Content	6	0.762	0.865	Sig at 0.01

From the previous table, it is clear that the stability coefficients in all midterm segments were high, indicating that the questionnaire has a high degree of stability.

2. **Alpha Cronbach's coefficient of persistence:** The researchers performed Alpha-Cronbach's persistence coefficients between each field separately, as shown in the following table:

Table 6: shows the coefficients of Alpha Cronbach for each of the domains of the scale of social networks

No.	Field	Coefficient Of Alpha-Cronbach Stability
1.	Website Administration	0.861
2.	Website Content	0.869

The overall correlation coefficient (0.924), a high stability coefficient, indicates the strength and validity of the scale. The researchers noted that the coefficients of the coefficients of the coefficients Pearson's correlations correlate with the results of Alpha-Cronbach's persistence coefficient.

Fifthly- Statistical Methods:

The computer was used in the statistical processing, especially the statistical packages program (SPSS), where all the data obtained by the researchers and then the results were extracted through the scientific equations necessary for this and the most important used in this study:

1. Averages, frequencies, standard deviations and percentages.
2. Spearman Brown's correlation coefficient for the equal half - division, and the Cronbach alpha factor to determine the stability of the resolution.
3. Pearson correlation coefficient to measure the relationship between variables.
4. Test T test for differences between averages.
5. One way Anova test for differences between averages.

7. TEST QUESTIONS AND STUDY HYPOTHESES

In order to answer the study questions and where the five-Likert scale was used in the preparation of the study instrument, the study adopted the following table to judge the trend when using the pentagram.

Table 7: Scale of measurements used in this study

Method / The Level	SMA	Relative weight%
Very Low	Less than (1.80)	Less than 36.00%
Low	From (1.80): (2.59)	From 36.00: 51.90%
Medium	From (2.60): (3.39)	From 52.00: 67.90%
High	From (3.40): (4.19)	From 68.00: 83.90%
Very High	Greater than (4.20)	Greater than 84.00%

This indicates that the averages of less than 1.80 indicate a very low degree in the elements of the field. The averages of (1.80: 2.59) indicate a low degree of availability of field elements, (2.60: 3.39) indicate that there is a medium degree in the elements of the field, and the averages ranging from (3.40: 4.19) indicate that there is a large degree in the elements of the field. More than (4.20) indicate that there is a very large degree in the field elements, on the scale used in the study shown in the previous table.

The first hypothesis test, which states:**There is a high level of use of social networks in technical colleges in Gaza Strip.**

To test this hypothesis, the researchers resorted to frequencies, averages, standard deviation, percentages, order and value of "T". The results were as shown in the following tables:

Table 8: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentages, Order, and Value of "T" for Sample Responses in Website Management

No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Relative Weight%	Item Order	P- Value Morality P- Value
1.	The college uses social networking networks to communicate with its students.	4.01	0.980	14.615	80.20%	1	0.000
2.	The college follows the students' responses to the college publications.	3.78	0.904	12.292	75.60%	2	0.000
3.	The College answers students' inquiries through social networks.	3.77	0.988	11.042	75.40%	3	0.000
4.	College websites are promoted on social networking sites through its website.	3.77	0.962	11.335	75.40%	4	0.000
5.	The college uses an "event creation" method to receive feedback from students about their upcoming activities.	3.54	0.943	8.152	70.80%	6	0.000
6.	The College is constantly interested in evaluating its social networking page.	3.61	0.947	9.143	72.20%	5	0.000
Total Domain		3.7455	0.81977	12.926	74.91%		0.000

The tabular value of "T" is at a degree of freedom (204) and at the level of significance (0.05) = 1.65

The tabular value of "T" is at the degree of freedom (204) and at the level of significance (0.01) = 2.34

Table (8) shows that through the "T" test of the related samples, all the areas of the site management area were calculated as "T" greater than the "T" value of the table. Thus, there is a statistical significance of the relative weight of the field. Social networks to communicate with her student) ranked first with a relative weight of (80.20%), which indicates the strong impact of this paragraph, while the fifth paragraph (the college uses the method of "creating an event" to receive response from students about its activities) (70.80%). The total score of the field obtained a relative weight of 74.91% which is a high level, that is, there is a high level of management of social networking sites in technical colleges.

Table 9: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentage, Order, and Value of "T" of Sample Responses in Website Content

No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Relative Weight%	Item Order	P- Value Morality P- Value
1.	The content of social networking sites is constantly updated.	3.76	0.939	11.468	75.20%	2	0.000
2.	The college uses the "Hashtag" tag to disseminate specific ideas.	3.53	0.995	7.584	70.60%	6	0.000
3.	The college uses videos to reach specific ideas for students.	3.68	0.979	9.872	73.60%	3	0.000
4.	The college uses the image as a way to communicate its ideas to students.	3.80	0.945	11.941	76.00%	1	0.000
5.	The college uses social networking as a platform for dialogue among students.	3.63	0.951	9.342	72.60%	5	0.000
6.	New updates are used consistently to change the content.	3.64	0.971	9.300	72.80%	4	0.000

Total Domain	3.6691	0.83911	11.334	73.38%		0.000
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The tabular value of "T" is at a degree of freedom (204) and at the level of significance (0.05) = 1.65

The tabular value of "T" is at the degree of freedom (204) and at the level of significance (0.01) = 2.34

Table (9) shows that through the test value of "T" for the relevant samples, all the terms of the content area of the site were calculated as "T" greater than the value of "T". Thus, there is a statistical significance of the relative weight of the paragraphs of this field. The college uses the image as a way to communicate its ideas to the students) on the first place with a relative weight of 76.00%, which indicates the strong influence of this paragraph, while the second paragraph (the college uses the tag "Hashtag" to publish certain ideas) in the last place with a relative weight (70.60%), and the total score of the field has a relative weight of (73.38%) which is high, that is as a high content of social networking sites in the technical colleges in Gaza Strip level.

Table 10: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentage, Order, and Value of "T" of Responses of Sample Members in All Areas and Degree of College of Scale

No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	Relative Weight%	Item Order	P- Value Morality P- Value
1.	Website Administration	3.7455	0.81977	12.926	74.91%	1	0.000
2.	Website Content	3.6691	0.83911	11.334	73.38%	2	0.000
Total degree of social networks		3.7073	0.79919	12.579	74.15%		0.000

The tabular value of "T" is at a degree of freedom (204) and at the level of significance (0.05) = 1.65

The tabular value of "T" is at the degree of freedom (204) and at the level of significance (0.01) = 2.34

Table (10) shows that in the T test of the related samples, all fields were calculated with a value greater than the T value. Thus, there is a statistical significance of the relative weight of these fields. (74.91%), while the second category (Website Content) came in second place with a relative weight (75.75%). The total score of the social networks reached a relative weight of 74.15% which is high, of the use of social networks in the technical colleges under study.

The second hypothesis test, which states:

There were statistically significant differences (0.05 α) in the use of social networks in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip according to the college variable.

To test this hypothesis, the analysis of mono-variance was used as in the following table:

Table 11: Analysis of the single variation of One Way Anova to find differences in the use of social networks depending on the college variable

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Website Administration	Between Groups	43.676	4	10.919	23.534	.000
	Within Groups	91.400	197	.464		
	Total	135.077	201			
Website Content	Between Groups	36.853	4	9.213	17.339	.000
	Within Groups	104.674	197	.531		
	Total	141.527	201			
Total degree of social networks	Between Groups	40.141	4	10.035	22.405	.000
	Within Groups	88.237	197	.448		
	Total	128.378	201			

The following table shows the existence of statistically significant differences in the use of social networks in all dimensions and degrees. This confirms the validity of the hypothesis. In order to know the direction of the differences, the LSD test was used as follows:

Table 12: Results of the LSD test for the direction of differences and their significance after the website management due to the college variable

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CIS	-				
UCAS	0.576359*	-			

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CCA	-0.179624	-0.755983*	-		
PTC	-0.001418	-0.577778*	0.178205	-	
GTC	-0.994276*	-1.570635*	-0.814652*	-0.992857*	-

* Sig. at level of significance (0.05)

From the previous table, there are differences in the management of the site between the University College of Applied Sciences (UCAS) and the other colleges in favor of UCAS and between the Gaza Training College (GTC) and the rest of the faculties for the benefit of the other colleges. This result can be explained by UNRWA's policy of not allowing the Gaza Training College to use the social media in the college.

Table 13: Results of LSD test for the direction of differences and their significance in the dimension of the Website Content due to the college variable

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CIS	-				
UCAS	0.574389*	-			
CCA	-0.084015	-0.658405*	-		
PTC	0.070686	-0.503704*	0.154701	-	
GTC	-0.876140*	-1.450529*	-0.792125*	-0.946825*	-

*Sig. at level of significance(0.05)

From the previous table, there are differences in the content of the site between the University College of Applied Sciences (UCAS) and the other colleges in favor of UCAS and between the Gaza Training College (GTC) and the rest of the faculties for the benefit of the other colleges. This result can be explained by UNRWA's policy of not allowing the Gaza Training College to use the social media in the college.

Table 14: Results of the LSD test for the direction of differences and their significance in the total score for the use of social networks due to the college variable

College	CIS	UCAS	CCA	PTC	GTC
CIS	-				
UCAS	0.575374*	-			
CCA	-0.131819	-0.707194*	-		
PTC	0.034634	-0.540741*	0.166453	-	
GTC	-0.935208*	-1.510582*	-0.803388*	-0.969841*	-

*Sig. at level of significance(0.05)

From the previous table, there are differences in the overall degree of use of social networks between the University College of Applied Sciences (UCAS) and the other colleges in favor of UCAS and between the Gaza Training College (GTC) and the rest of the faculties for the benefit of the other colleges. This result can be explained by UNRWA's policy of not allowing the Gaza Training College to use the social media in the college.

The second hypothesis test, which states:

There were statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the use of social networks in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip according to the variable of social awareness.

To test this hypothesis, the analysis of mono-variance was used as in the following table:

Table 15: Analysis of Independent sample T test to find differences in the use of social networks depending on the gender variable

	Gender	N	Mean	t	df	Sig
Website Administration	Male	156	3.6908	-1.756525	200	0.08
	Female	46	3.9312			
Website Content	Male	156	3.6303	-1.211645	200	0.23

	Female	46	3.8007			
Total degree of social networks	Male	156	3.6606	-1.536776	200	0.13
	Female	46	3.8659			

In the previous table, there are no statistically significant differences between males and females in the use of social networks in colleges.

8. CONCLUSIONS

1. The results confirmed the existence of a high degree of approval for the dimensions of the social networks and a relative weight (74.15%) according to the perspective of the employees of the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip.
2. The results of the study showed a high level of social networking areas (site management and Website Content) in the technical colleges in the Gaza Strip. The field of site management ranked first with a relative weight of (74.91%). And a relative weight (73.38%).
3. The results showed that there are differences between colleges in the use of social networks, where the results showed that the most common colleges used these networks is (UCAS) and the least used is (GTC).
4. The results showed no differences between male and female employees in the use of social networks in technical colleges.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings of the researchers, it recommends the following:

1. The need to raise awareness of the importance of Facebook and other social networking sites by holding courses for employees in technical colleges and introducing them in ways of optimal use of such sites, and the benefits of this use, which will be reflected positively on the technical colleges.
2. Adopting dealing with various social media sites as real, and on Palestinian and Arab technical colleges, using them in accordance with the objectives of technical colleges.
3. Urge the management of technical colleges to devote time to their presence on social networks to follow the public and respond to their queries.
4. The use of social networks and the possibilities and capabilities of active and vital, and the investment of social networks and use them in all areas of life.
5. The need for decision-makers in technical colleges to focus on social sites, because they are an important and effective means of communication, and are the link between beneficiaries and decision-makers.
6. To promote the use of modern electronic means of work and the need to increase the link of customers to the College through electronic services.

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